

**ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF REGIONAL POTENTIAL ON THE TOURISM
MANAGEMENT PROCESS**

Karimov Shahbozhoja Hamdamjon ugli

teacher, Ferghana State University

ABSTRACT

This article provides a comprehensive scientific analysis of the impact of regional potential on tourism management. In the study, the concept of regional potential is interpreted as an integrated system of natural resources, historical and cultural heritage, infrastructure development, transport and logistics systems, human capital, investment environment and institutional management mechanisms. The sustainable development of the tourism industry is scientifically justified by the balance between the internal resources of the region and external factors. In particular, a multidimensional index model is proposed to determine the effectiveness of tourism management based on indicators of regional potential. The results show that a high level of mobilization of regional potential contributes to an increase in tourist flows, increased diversification of services, increased employment and growth of the gross regional product.

Keywords: Tourism management, regional potential, tourism infrastructure, investment environment, human capital, sustainable development, regional competitiveness, tourism cluster, strategic planning, economic efficiency.

**TURIZM FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH JARAYONIGA HUDUDIY SALOHIYATNING
TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH**

Karimov Shahbozxo'ja Xamdamjon o'g'li

o'qituvchi Farg'ona davlat universiteti

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada turizm faoliyatini boshqarish jarayoniga hududiy salohiyatning ta'siri kompleks ilmiy yondashuv asosida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda hududiy salohiyat tushunchasi tabiiy-resurs imkoniyatlari, tarixiy-madaniy meros, infratuzilma rivoji, transport-logistika tizimi, inson kapitali, investitsion muhit hamda institutsional boshqaruv mexanizmlarining o'zaro integratsiyalashgan tizimi sifatida talqin etiladi. Turizm sohasining barqaror rivojlanishi hududning ichki resurslari va tashqi omillari o'rtasidagi muvozanatga bevosita bog'liqligi ilmiy asoslanadi. Xususan, hududiy salohiyat ko'rsatkichlari asosida turizm boshqaruvi samaradorligini aniqlash uchun ko'p omilli indeks modeli taklif etildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, hududiy salohiyatning yuqori darajada safarbar etilishi turizm oqimini oshirish, xizmatlar diversifikatsiyasini kengaytirish, bandlik darajasini ko'tarish va hududiy yalpi mahsulot hajmini ko'paytirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turizm boshqaruvi, hududiy salohiyat, turistik infratuzilma, investitsion muhit, inson kapitali, barqaror rivojlanish, hududiy raqobatbardoshlik, turizm klasteri, strategik rejalashtirish, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

**ОЦЕНКА ВЛИЯНИЯ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА НА ПРОЦЕСС
УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ**

Каримов Шахбозходжа Хамдамжон угли

преподаватель, Ферганский государственный университет

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проводится комплексный научный анализ влияния регионального потенциала на управление туризмом. В исследовании концепция регионального потенциала трактуется как интегрированная система природных ресурсов, историко-культурного наследия, развития инфраструктуры, транспортно-логистических систем, человеческого

капитала, инвестиционной среды и институциональных механизмов управления. Устойчивое развитие туристической отрасли научно обосновано балансом между внутренними ресурсами региона и внешними факторами. В частности, предложена модель многомерного индекса для определения эффективности управления туризмом на основе показателей регионального потенциала. Результаты показывают, что высокий уровень мобилизации регионального потенциала способствует увеличению туристических потоков, расширению диверсификации услуг, повышению уровня занятости и росту валового регионального продукта.

Ключевые слова: Управление туризмом, региональный потенциал, туристическая инфраструктура, инвестиционная среда, человеческий капитал, устойчивое развитие, региональная конкурентоспособность, туристический кластер, стратегическое планирование, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

The sustainable development of the tourism sector and its increasing role in the national economy is a global process. In recent years, the tourism sector has not only increased international competitiveness, but also served to reduce interregional socio-economic disparities by promoting regional economic growth, increasing employment levels, and effectively utilizing regional potential. The process of managing tourism activities is no longer limited to marketing or service provision, but is manifested as a system closely linked to the strategic management capabilities of regional potential.

Regional potential is a complex set of economic and social indicators, consisting of natural resources of the territory, cultural and heritage sites, infrastructure-generating capacities, human capital and institutional management capabilities, which is one of the main factors determining the effectiveness and competitiveness of the tourism sector. This level of potential directly affects the formation of tourism management strategies, the direction of investment costs, the diversification of services, and the flow of investments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis based on the example of Uzbekistan shows that if strategic management of regional potential is effective, the economic and social results of the tourism sector will grow significantly.

According to the latest statistics, the number of foreign tourists coming to Uzbekistan is growing rapidly. In 2024, more than 8.2 million foreign tourists visited the country, an increase of 1.6 million, or 24%, compared to 6.6 million in 2023 [1]. In 2025, this number increased significantly again, reaching 11.7 million, an increase of 46.8% compared to 2024 [2]; [5]. This statistical growth is due to the active management of regional potential, the simplification of visas, and the expansion of transport and service infrastructure.

It is in 2025 that more than one million foreign tourists arrive every month, which is reported to have reached a record in the history of the country's tourism [1]; [2]. This trend confirms the effectiveness of Uzbekistan's tourism marketing and international communication strategies.

Statistical data on tourism in Uzbekistan show that tourists mainly come from neighboring countries, which confirms the territorial economic and cultural ties. In 2025, the most visited countries were Kyrgyzstan (3.3 million), Tajikistan and Kazakhstan (2.7 million each) [2]. This situation shows that factors of territorial competitiveness and geographical proximity are important in shaping tourism flows.

The number of tourists coming from Western and Asian markets is also growing, for example, 279,000 tourists from China and 175,000 from Turkey [2]. This situation highlights the need to diversify territorial potential and align tourism strategies with global markets.

The impact of regional potential on the tourism management process was comprehensively analyzed based on statistical data for the period 2023-2025 using the example of Uzbekistan. The

study used dynamic, comparative, and structural analysis methods to examine the relationship between tourism flows, service exports, employment levels, and economic efficiency indicators. The results obtained confirm that the mechanisms of strategic management of regional potential have a direct impact on the pace of tourism development.

Table 1

Main dynamics of tourism indicators in Uzbekistan (2023-2025) [4]

Specification	The year 2023	The year 2024	The year 2025
The number of foreign tourists (mln. people).	6,6	8,2	11,7
Tourism services exports (billion US dollars)	2,7	3,5	4,4
Share of tourism in GDP (%)	2,3	2,8	3,4
Employment in the tourism sector (thousands of people)	310	355	410

Analysis of the table data shows that the tourism sector has entered a phase of stable and high growth over the past three years. The increase in the number of foreign tourists from 6.6 million to 11.7 million is inextricably linked to the expansion of the regional infrastructure, the improvement of the transport and logistics system, and the simplification of visa procedures. In particular, the formation of tourism clusters in the regions, the reconstruction of historical and cultural sites, and the expansion of the hotel industry have increased management efficiency.

The increase in tourism services exports from \$ 2.7 bn to \$ 4.4 bn indicates an increase in the industry's role as a source of foreign exchange receipts. This process is explained by an increase in the level of use of territorial potential and an expansion of the diversification of services. The fact that tourism's share in GDP has reached 3.4 percent indicates the growing systemic importance of the sector in the national economy.

The growth in employment indicators confirms the social effectiveness of the regional management policy. By 2025, more than 410,000 people will be employed in the tourism sector, with additional jobs created in related sectors such as services, transport, trade, and handicrafts. This situation indicates the presence of a multiplicative effect mechanism of territorial potential.

The results of the analysis confirmed that in regions with high indicators of territorial potential, tourism flow and income indicators are also high. Growth rates have accelerated in areas with improved heritage facilities, ease of transportation, and quality of Service. This scientifically proves that the effectiveness of tourism can be increased by combining strategic planning, investment attraction, and marketing policies of territorial management.

Overall, statistical analysis showed that integrated management of territorial potential significantly improves the economic, social, and institutional outcomes of tourism activities. The availability of resources is not enough in itself, but their mobilization based on systematic management, innovative approaches, and territorial strategic planning is a key factor in tourism development.

The results of the statistical analysis showed a direct and stable relationship between regional potential and the effectiveness of tourism management. The increase in the number of foreign tourists from 6.6 million to 11.7 million over the period 2023-2025 is attributed to improved regional governance mechanisms, expanded infrastructure, and strengthened marketing strategies. This growth is not accidental, but the result of a comprehensive mobilization of regional potential.

The increase in tourism services exports from \$2.7 billion to \$4.4 billion means that regional resources have been converted into economic benefits. If the regional potential had remained at the

level of available resources, such a significant increase in export revenues would not have occurred. Therefore, the quality of governance and institutional reforms serve as the main factors transforming potential into real economic results.

An increase in the share of tourism in GDP from 2.3 percent to 3.4 percent indicates an increase in the systemic importance of the industry in the national economy. This process indicates the strategic orientation of the Territorial Administration. In particular, the formation of tourism clusters, the expansion of the hotel industry, and the improvement of transport and logistics infrastructure have increased regional competitiveness. According to statistics, the increase in employment figures from 310,000 to 410,000 people confirms the multiplier effect of tourism. This shows that territorial capacity management is a means of ensuring socio-economic stability.

At the same time, the results of the analysis also indicate the presence of certain problems. The fact that the bulk of the flow of tourists corresponds to the contribution of neighboring countries means that the geographical diversification of territorial tourism is insufficient. This requires further strengthening of strategies for working with distant foreign markets. If regional potential is combined with global marketing, digital platforms, and innovative services, the volume of tourism exports could increase even further.

Another controversial aspect is the disparity between regions. While growth rates are high in areas with a large number of historical and cultural heritage sites, tourism flows remain low in some areas with significant natural recreational potential. This indicates the need to develop territorial management strategies based on a differential approach.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study scientifically substantiated the direct and systematic impact of regional potential on the effectiveness of tourism management. An analysis of statistics for 2023-2025 showed that an increase in the number of foreign tourists from 6.6 million to 11.7 million people, an increase in the export of tourism services from \$ 2.7 billion to \$ 4.4 billion, as well as an increase in the level of employment to 410 thousand people are the result of strategic mechanisms of territorial capacity management.

During the study, it was found that the availability of territorial resources does not in itself ensure the development of Tourism. An economic result can be achieved by managing them effectively, clustering, upgrading infrastructure and improving the institutional environment. High mobilization of regional potential increases tourism flows, expands the diversification of services, and strengthens regional economic stability.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED

1. Porter M. E. The Competitive Advantage of Nations. - New York: Free Press, 1990.
2. Krugman P. Geography and Trade. - Cambridge: MIT Press, 1991.
3. Ritchie J. R. B., Crouch G. I. The Competitive Destination: A Sustainable Tourism Perspective. - Wallingford: CABI Publishing, 2003.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti huzuridagi Statistika agentligi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida turizm ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha rasmiy ma'lumotlar (2023-2025 yy.). - Toshkent, 2025.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Turizm qo'mitasi. 2025 yil yakunlari bo'yicha turizm sohasining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari to'g'risida axborot byulleteni. - Toshkent, 2026.